

Controlling the crystal growth of potassium iodide with 1,1'-bis(pyridin-4-ylmethyl)-2,2'-biimidazole ligand (L) – formation of linear $[K_4I_4]_n$ polymer with nearly cubic $[K_4I_4]$ core units.

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Abstract: Crystal growth of potassium iodide was controlled by using neutral organic (1,1'-bis(pyridin-4-ylmethyl)-2,2'-biimidazole (further L) ligand as the modifier. Selected modifier allows to maintain original cubic $[K_4I_4]$ units and arrange them into a linear 1D ligand-supported chain. The N-K binding of the ligand to KI salt, as well as I \cdots H, N \cdots H, and N \cdots I weak interactions stabilize the structure to create a unique $[K_4I_4]_n$ 1D polymer of original potassium iodide ionic salt inside of the $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ complex.

Controlled crystal growth is an important method in tuning physicochemical properties of compounds in solid state.^[1] Various compounds can inhibit or promote crystal growth and, thus, have been used for controlling it.^[2-4] Interactions between crystallizing solute and a modifier compound can range from covalent bonds to non-covalent interactions such as van der Waals interactions, electrostatic, hydrogen bonding, and π - π stacking.² To obtain the desired impact on the crystal growth, a modifier must be carefully designed with consideration to all possible forms of interactions.

Growth of an inorganic salt, such as KI, can be controlled physically by space limitation or chemically by using modifier molecules that limits the free 3D self-assembled growth of KI units. Sloan et al. have used the physical approach to limit the growth of KI within a single wall carbon nanotube (SWCNT). It has been shown that it is possible to grow a 1D KI chain consisting of repeating cubic K_4I_4 units by using SWCNT with 1.2–1.6 nm median diameter. Although the cubic basic structures of the repeating $[K_4I_4]$ units resembled closely to those found in pure KI, some distortions of K-I distances and K-I-K angles were observed.^[5] Inside the restricted space of SWCNT, only one-dimensional growth was possible and further modifications of KI were inaccessible. The chemical approach allows to control and modify growth of potassium iodide. There have been several attempts to organize potassium iodide into continuous structure with organic and metalorganic molecules. Kruszynski *et al.*, have synthesized hybrid net compound using hexamethyltetraamine (htma) ligands that are bonded to K atoms through the nitrogen atoms of the ligands. The presence of htma molecules promotes the growth of nearly linear 1D chains of K-I-K-I. Furthermore, the htma molecules link the neighboring chains into parallel bundles. However, in this case the pure KI cubic K_4I_4 units are lost and replaced with a simple chain.^[6] Rhodium tetracarboxylates have also been inserted into the continuous KI structure giving more or less planar arrangement of K and I as shown by Amo-Ochoa *et al.*^[7] Liu *et al.*, have reported the structure of $[Cu_2K(Mtta)_2]$ (where Mtta is deprotonated 5-methyl-1H-tetrazole) the KI units can be seen as a chain of “opened potassium iodide cubes”, where Cu and the two nitrogen atoms of the Mtta ligand are inserted in one edge of the cubes.^[8] Using 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenantroline ligands Buttery *et al.*, have obtained even more opened structure, where the length of the KI chain has been limited to six K and four I atoms.^[9] However, in all of the structures described above the original cubic arrangement of pure KI is either heavily distorted or completely lost and used chemical additives cannot really be seen as modifiers for crystal growth.

By using 1,1'-bis(pyridin-4-ylmethyl)-2,2'-biimidazole (L) as the chemical modifier we succeed to obtain the first 1D polymeric structure that retains the original cubic K_4I_4 structure of KI (**Figure 1**). In the ligand supported polymer of $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ the K_4I_4 cubes are repeated only in one direction. The 1D polymeric compound was obtained in the reaction of KI with 1,1'-bis(pyridin-4-ylmethyl)-2,2'-biimidazole (L) in methanol under ambient conditions. To obtain $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ product with a reasonable yield an excess of KI was added in the reaction mixture. The X-Ray quality crystals were obtained by allowing the solvent to evaporate slowly. The polymer growth was driven by self-assembly of the components; however, the detailed mechanism is not clear (**Figure 1**). According to the solid state studies (see Supporting Information, Solid State Studies) $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ polymer was found to be stable in air under ambient conditions. Liquid state studies (see Supporting Information, Liquid State Studies) of the $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ revealed that in methanol solution coordination of the ligand to potassium iodide is lost, and the structure collapses back to the K^+ and I^- ions releasing the neutral ligand.

According to the single crystal XRD data nearly cubic $[K_4I_4]_n$ units in the structure are supported by the ligands (**Figure 2**). In the distorted octahedral coordination sphere of each K atom, there are four I atoms and two pyridine nitrogen atoms of ligands. K_4I_4 core units of the $K_4I_4L_4$ structure closely resemble the cubic structure of the crystalline KI. In the crystalline KI the K-I distances are 3.525 Å and the K-I-K angles and I-K-I angles 90°.^{ref} In $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ cube the K-I distances range from 3.4759(4) Å to 3.5674(5) Å, K-I-K and I-K-I angles within the cube range from 86.336(13)° to 89.198(11)° and from 90.397(10)° to 96.490(13)° respectively, as well as K-N distances slightly differ being 2.815(2) Å and 2.906(2) Å (Fig. X2).

Figure 1. Formation of polymeric $[K_4L_4]_n$ chain.

Figure 2. Top: left – ligand; right – $[K_4L_4]$ unit. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles ($^\circ$): K1-I1 = K3-I3: 3.5037(5), K2-I2 = K4-I4 = K1-I3 = K3-I1: 3.5674(5), K4-I2 = K2-I4: 3.5037(5), K1-I2 = K2-I1 = K3-I4 = K4-I3: 3.4759(4), K-N: 2.815(2) and 2.906(2). K-I-K angles of the supported unit range from 86.336(13) to 89.198(11) and the I-K-I angles from 90.397(10) to 96.490(13). Bottom: A chain of three $[K_4L_4]$ units. K-I distance between the units (A): 3.4712(5) Å and within the unit (B): 3.4759(4) Å. K-I-K and I-K-I angles between the supported units along the chain: 170.41(2) $^\circ$.

Two ligand-supported cubes are connected with direct K-I bonds (3.4712 Å, bond B in **Figure 2**), that are slightly shorter than K-I bonds within the cubes (3.5674 Å, bond A in **Figure 2**). The K-I-K and I-K-I angles between the neighboring cubes in the polymer are 170.41(2) $^\circ$, while in pure KI corresponding K-I-K or I-K-I angles are equal 180 $^\circ$. Despite the slight distortion of the K_4L_4 unit within the $[K_4L_4]_n$ polymer, the basic cubic arrangement of K_4L_4 core is retained comparing to the pure KI. However, the geometry of ligands forces K_4L_4 units to only form a linear $[K_4L_4]_n$ polymer chain, and not a 3D polymer. The 1,1'-bis(pyridin-4-ylmethyl)-2,2'-biimidazole ligand was found to be extremely selective towards growth of KI-based 1D-polymer, and no other alkali metal halide 1D-polymers were obtained at the same conditions. Likewise, use of a similar ligand 1,1'-bis(pyridin-3-ylmethyl)-2,2'-biimidazole with the 3rd position of nitrogen instead of 4th in pyridyl ring failed to produce polymeric structure due to the change in the ligand geometry.

The impact of the supporting ligands on the stability of the $[K_4I_4]_n$ chain-like structure was studied computationally.^[10–14] Models comprising of 1, 2, and 3 $K_4I_4L_4$ units were cut directly from the crystal structure and analyzed without geometry optimization. The energetics of the corresponding linear $[K_4I_4]_n$ models, obtained from the crystal structure of pure KI, were also analyzed and compared with the ligand supported models.

Single point energies of $[K_4I_4]_n$ and $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ ($n=1-3$) were calculated. In both series the $n=1$ case was set as reference with zero energy. Then the stabilization energies obtained by adding the second and the third cube to the models ($n=2$ and 3) were calculated. The two series were compared to see if the presence of ligand had any impact on stability of the growing chain. The results are summarized in the Supporting Information, (Computational studies. Results and Discussion. **Tables S2-S3** and **Figures S5-S7**). The addition of new cubes ($[K_4I_4L_4]$ or $[K_4I_4]$) into the chain stabilizes the growing structure in both cases as expected. However, the stabilization effect is emphasized in the case of ligand substituted $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ model. Therefore, the growth of the ligand-supported 1D-polymer is energetically favored over the growth of pure KI.

Selected properties of the electron density of $[K_4I_4]_n$, $[K_4I_4]_n[K_4I_4]_{2n}$ and $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ models (for visualization of the models see the Supporting Information, **Figures S5 and S7**) were analyzed by Quantum Theory of Atoms in Molecules (QTAIM) to study the effect of the ligands on the nature of the interactions. According to calculations when the $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ chain forms nature of the $K\cdots I$ interactions remains essentially the same as in the cubic $[K_4I_4]_n$ without supporting ligands, even though the interaction of the ligand nitrogens with the potassium ions is fairly strong, 13-16 kJmol^{-1} . All $K\cdots I$ and $I\cdots I$ interactions are clearly electrostatic, since the ratio of potential energy density and kinetic energy density is less than 1, and only a negligible amount of electron sharing is involved, as indicated by the very small value of delocalization index. The ligands form additional weak hydrogen bonding interactions $I\cdots H$ and $N\cdots H$, as well as $\pi\cdots\pi$ and $N\cdots I$ interactions, which have a further role in the stabilization. Notably, the interactions remain the same even in the larger 3D models of the crystals.

In conclusion, for the first time, potassium iodide was successfully organized into unique 1D chain of almost cubic $[K_4I_4]_n$ units with a help of biimidazole-based organic ligand. Through the fairly strong $N\cdots K$ interactions, weak $I\cdots H$ and $N\cdots H$ hydrogen bonding, and weak $N\cdots I$ interactions $[K_4I_4]_n$ chain is organized and supported by the ligands in solid state. This self-assembled potassium iodide-based hybrid material was characterized with several physicochemical methods, and it was confirmed that the structure exists only in solid state and collapses in solution back to the starting materials.

According to computational studies, extension of $[K_4I_4L_4]_n$ chain leads to a larger change in the stabilization energy than extension of $[K_4I_4]_n$ chain, and weak interactions play an important role in the stabilization of the structure. The geometry and flexibility of the ligand, as well as additional weak interactions with ionic salt influenced the growth of the reported potassium iodide 1D polymer. Therefore, considering all possible forms of interactions, it is possible to design an appropriate ligand to control crystal growth of an ionic salt.

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